

BENAKI
PHYTOPATHOLOGICAL
INSTITUTE

International workshop

Preparatory work on how to report, use and interpret historical control data in (eco)toxicity studies

Virtual event, (via Zoom), 3-5 May 2022, 12:00 – 16:00 Central European Time (CET)

Day 1: 3rd May 2022 (12:00-16:00 CET)

Chair: Martin Wilks, Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology		
Co-Chair: consortium team		
12:00-12:30	Welcome, Scope of the workshop Short feedback from the survey	Tamara Coja, AGES and Agathi Charistou, BPI (on behalf of consortium)
12:30 – 13:15	Standardization and Biosecurity in Laboratory Rodent Breeding	Urte Jäh, Jutta Davidson (Charles River Laboratories)
13:15 - 13:45	National Toxicology Program's Perspective and Use of Historical Control Data	Chad Blystone, (National toxicology Programme, NTP)
13:45 – 14:15	Use of HCD data on Pharmaceutical Toxicology Studies at Charles River Edinburgh	Aidan McGuire (Charles River Laboratories)
14:15 – 14:45	Challenges in using the HCD: a methodological perspective	Laura Martino (EFSA)
14:45 – 15:00	Coffee break	
15:00 – 16:00	Panel discussion	

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Day 2: 4th May 2022 (12:00-16:00 CET)

Chair: Diane Benford (Vice-chair of EFSA Scientific Committee)		
Co-Chair: consortium team		
12:00-12:15	Wrap up Day 1	Agathi Charistou, BPI (on behalf of consortium)
12:15 – 13:00	Historical Control Data in Pathology: Meaningful Use and Limitations	Sibylle Gröters, (on behalf of RITA-group)
13:00 - 13:30	How to report, use and interpret historical control data in DART studies	Manon Beekhuijzen (Charles River Laboratories)
13:30 – 14:00	Establishment and Use of Historical Control Data in Clinical Pathology	Volker Strauss (on behalf of ESTP)
14:00 – 14:30	Assessing the Quality of Historical Control Distributions and Calculating Useful Intervals: Genetic Toxicology Examples	Stephen Dertinger (Litronlabs)
14:30 – 14:45	Coffee break	
14:45 – 16:00	Panel discussion	

Day 3: 5th May 2022 (12:00-16:00 CET)

Chair: Manuela Tiramani (EFSA Pesticides Peer Review Unit)		
Co-Chair: consortium team		
12:00-12:15	Wrap up Day 2	Agathi Charistou, BPI (on behalf of consortium)
12:15 – 12:35	ANSES experience - pesticide evaluation in the area of mammalian toxicology	Adeline Cavelier, Bertrand Desprez (ANSES)
12:35 - 12:55	Experience from the European pesticide, biocide and C&L evaluation – Competent Authority perspective	Susanne Rudzok (BfR)
12:55 – 13:15	Historical control data in CLH dossiers	Chiara Perazzolo (ECHA)
13:15 – 13:30	Coffee break	
13:30 – 13:50	Acceptability and Use of Historical Control Data in Toxicological Studies	Thomas Hofmann (on behalf of Crop Life Europe)
13:50 – 14:10	Experience from the European pesticide evaluation – NGO perspective	Peter Clausing (PAN Germany)
14:10 – 14:30	Avian reproductive toxicity studies – ecotoxicologist perspective	Manousos Foudoulakis (Corteva), Thomas Bean (FMC)
14:30 – 14:45	Coffee break	
14:45 – 15:45	Panel discussion	
15:45– 16:00	Wrap up of the workshop	Tamara Coja, AGES (coordinator, on behalf of consortium)